

Brassinosteroids, New Class of Phytohormones[†]

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Brassinosteroids are a new class of phytohormones with their role as stress and pathogenic disease resistance in plants as well as high plant growth promoting activity. Due to their availability in minute amounts from natural sources and worldwide studies on the application of brassinosteroids for the enhancement of yields of variety of agricultural crops, there have been intensified research efforts towards the synthesis of this class of phytohormones. In this review, we have demonstrated our efforts towards the synthesis of brassinosteroids.

The first real confirmation of the role of steroids as hormones in higher plants was found in 1979 when scientists at the United States Department of Agriculture established the structure of a new steroid¹ named brassinolide **1**. They isolated 4 mg of this steroid **1** from 40 kg of bee collected pollen of rape plant (*Brassica napus* L.). It produced a powerful growth accelerating effect when applied to young pinto bean plants. The increase in growth was both due to cell elongation and cell division. Its structure was elucidated as (2*R*,3*S*,22*R*,23*R*,24*S*)-2,3,22,23-tetrahydroxy-24-methyl-B-homo-7-oxa-5 α -cholestan-6-one **1** by spectroscopic data as well as X-ray. It is the first naturally occurring steroid with an unprecedented seven-membered B-ring lactone and two vicinal *cis* diol functions at ring-A and in the side-chain. The discovery of brassinolide **1** is the most important one to the plant physiologists and biochemists, since the discovery of gibberellic acid which causes increase in growth due to cell expansion only.

Brassinolide **1** and its analogues collectively known as brassinosteroids, are a new class of steroidal phytohormones with high growth-promoting and antistress activities. It was believed that the process of hormonal signaling in plants is fundamentally different from that in higher mammals. But work reported^{2,3} in 1996 by two independent groups, one in USA and the other in Germany, made these beliefs obsolete. These two groups have found the first evidence that steroid hormones, long known to be important in animals, also play a key role in plants. Brassinosteroids may constitute a distinct class of phytohormones with an important role in light-regulated development of higher plants. These

findings are a remarkable demonstration of evolutionary conservation between plants and animals and clearly show that steroid hormones are vital to both plant and animal development.

At the present time more than sixty brassinosteroids have been detected⁴ in a wide variety of plants. The detected amounts vary from 0.1 ng/kg (ethylbrassinone **7**, from fruit of *Brassica Campestris* var. *pekinensis*) upto 100 μ g/kg (brassinolide **1**, from the pollen of *Brassica napus* L.). Thirty one of them are fully characterised, including twenty-nine free compounds and two conjugates. A few representative members of the brassinosteroid⁵ family are listed in Chart 1.

Structurally they exhibit either 7-membered B-ring lactone but differing in C-24 substituent of the side-chain moiety **1-5** or they are the corresponding 6-oxosteroids with normal 6-membered B-ring **6-11**. 6-Deoxycastasterone **14**, 6-deoxydolicosterone **15** and 6-deoxyhomodolicosterone **16** lack the B-ring oxygen function. All the brassinosteroids are (2*R*,3*S*,22*R*,23*R*)-tetrols with the exception of 2-deoxycastasterone (typhasterol **12**) and teasterone **13** which possess only one (3*R*)- or (3*S*)-hydroxy group in ring-A respectively.

Because of its scarcity, worldwide studies on the application of brassinosteroids for the enhancement of yield of a variety of agricultural crops and a clearly positive result⁶ in field-trials from India and China have intensified the research efforts towards the synthesis of brassinosteroids.

Synthesis of brassinosteroids

Soon after the structure elucidation of brassinolide **1**, its first syntheses were published^{7,8}. In view of extremely low brassinosteroid content in plants ($C = 10^{-5}$ to $10^{-12}\%$), method of isolation from natural raw material cannot be considered as a practical source of brassinosteroids. As a result, brassinosteroid synthesis^{5,7-10} has remained a field of tremendous activity for the past eighteen years. Total synthesis is obviously only of theoretical interest¹¹, since it requires the formation of exceptionally complex stereo-

[†]Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

Chart 1

chemistry of these compounds with as many as 13 chiral centers. Even a partial synthesis is an extremely complex task, particularly the formation of a polyfunctional side-chain with four contiguous chiral centers at C-20, C-22, C-23 and C-24. For the chemical synthesis of brassinosteroids, starting from a suitable steroid precursor, the typical A/B ring functionalisation and the construction of dihydroxylated side-chain moiety including the asymmetric centers at the side-chain are necessary.

A/B Ring functionalisation :

In nearly all syntheses of brassinosteroids (Scheme 1), a Δ^5 -3 β -hydroxy starting steroid 17 is transformed to Δ^2 -6-oxo compound 24 which is suitable intermediate for the synthesis of both 6-oxo- and 6-oxo-7-oxalactone type brassinosteroids. The Δ^2 -6-oxo compound 24 obtained by different methods, when reacted with catalytic amount of OsO_4 in the presence of *N*-methylmorpholine-*N*-oxide

(NMO), results in stereospecific dihydroxylation to the (2*R*, 3*S*)-dihydroxy-6-oxo compound 29, thus yielding typical A/B ring structural features of the native brassinosteroids 6-11. Subsequent Baeyer-Villiger oxidation of 29 gives upto 90% of the desired 7-oxalactone 30.

Side-chain construction :

Stereoselective synthesis of brassinolide side-chain poses a real synthetic challenge due to the presence of four contiguous chiral centers at C-20, C-22, C-23 and C-24 along with two hydroxyl groups at C-22 and C-23. A number of reports^{5,7-10} regarding the stereoselective synthesis of brassinolide side-chain have appeared in the literature. In some of the syntheses, 22,23-diol functionality is introduced into the steroidal precursor with an intact sterol side-chain. But introduction of the 22,23-diol with catalytic amount of OsO_4 and NMO always furnishes¹² the unnatural (22*S*,23*S*)-diol as the major product. Recently, a practical method¹³ for the stereoselective construction of the side-chain has been reported which involves direct OsO_4 catalysed asymmetric dihydroxylation of readily available (22*E*)-24-alkyl unsaturated side-chain to give naturally occurring (22*R*,23*R*)-isomer as the major product. In majority of the methods for the construction of brassinolide side-chain, C-22 aldehyde 31 was chosen as the starting material.

During the last few years we have been interested in the synthesis of brassinosteroids starting from readily available steroidal precursors. Now we would like to present our efforts in this area. Two efficient and stereoselective syntheses of (20*S*)-3 α ,5-cyclo-6 β -methoxy-5 α -pregnan-20-carboxaldehyde 31 have been achieved, starting from 3 β -hydroxyandrost-5-ene-17-one 32¹⁴ (Scheme 2) and also from 16-dehydropregnenolone acetate 39¹⁵ (Scheme 3). This C-22 aldehyde 31 is a crucial starting material for the synthesis¹⁶ of a large number of brassinosteroids and other steroids. The 17-ketosteroid 32 was converted to (*Z*)-17(20)-ethylidene steroid 33 in 89% yield via Wittig reaction using 2 equivalents of $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{PCH}_2\text{CH}_3\text{I}$ and simple workup procedure (Scheme 2). Compound 33 on treatment with toluene-*p*-sulfonyl chloride in pyridine furnished the tosylate 34 in 90% yield. Ene reaction on 34 with paraformaldehyde in the presence of acetic anhydride using various cation exchange resins as catalysts afforded stereospecifically the C-22 acetate 35 in excellent yield. The ene reaction carried out using cation exchange resins, stereospecifically generates the natural configuration at C-20. For the first time, cation exchange resins have been used as catalysts in the ene reaction. Compound 35 was converted to C-22 aldehyde 31 using simple reaction sequence. The 22-acetate 35 on treatment with pyridine in anhydrous methanol afforded the 3,5-cyclo compound 36 (89%). This 36 on hydrogenation over Pd/C furnished the saturated compound 37 with natural con-

Scheme 1. Reagents and condition: (a) K_2CO_3 , acetone, $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{KOAc}$, acetone, H_2O , (b) Jones reagent, (c) DMSO , NaOAc , (d) AcOH , H_2SO_4 , $\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3/\text{HCl}$, AcOH/HBr , AcOH , (e) Li_2CO_3 , LiBr , DMF , (f) PTSA , sulpholan/ LiBr , PPTS , DMF , (g) BF_3 , THF , (h) Jones reagent/ PCC , (i) K_2CO_3 , acetone, H_2O , (j) CrO_3 , Py , (k) Li , NH_3 , (l) 4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazolin-3,5-dione, (m) Li EtNH_2 , (n) OsO_4 , NMO , (o) $\text{CF}_3\text{CO}_3\text{H}$, (p) *m*-CPBA.

Scheme 2

figuration at C-17 (98%). Hydrolysis of 37 with methanolic KOH afforded the alcohol 38, which on oxidation with pyridinium chlorochromate furnished the aldehyde 31. The conversion of 17-ketosteroid 32 to aldehyde 31 is achieved¹⁴

in seven steps with 59% overall yield. The second route¹⁵ for the synthesis of the C-22 aldehyde 31 starts from 16-dehydropregnenolone acetate 39. The important feature of this synthesis is stereospecific generation of the acetate 35

Scheme 3. Reagents and condition : (a) $Ti(i-Pr)_3Cl$, CH_2Cl_2 , $(CH_2O)_n$, 25° , 4.5 h, Ac_2O , Py, 24 h, (b) $TMSCl$, CH_2Cl_2 , $(CH_2O)_n$, 25° , 4 h, Ac_2O , Py, 24 h, (c) $TBDMSCl$, CH_2Cl_2 , $(CH_2O)_n$, 25° , 4 h, Ac_2O , Py, 24 h.

through ene reaction using three different catalysts (Scheme 3).

Selective hydrogenation of the C-16 double bond of 16-dehydropregnenolone acetate **39** using 5% Pd/C in ethyl acetate, hydrolysis of the acetate group by potassium hydroxide in *t*-butanol followed by the protection of the 3β -hydroxy using *t*-butyldimethylsilyl chloride in DMF in the presence of imidazole and reduction of the C-20 ketone with LAH in THF yielded C-20 epimeric alcohols **40** and **41**, in four steps with an overall yield of 84% in the ratio 9 : 1. These alcohols **40** and **41** separately or as a mixture on dehydration with phosphorous oxychloride and pyridine afforded the required (*Z*)-olefin **42** (88%). The desilylation of C-3 alcohol followed by protection as tosylate furnished the tosylate **34** in excellent yield. Ene reaction of **34** with paraformaldehyde as an enophile and titanium trisisopropoxy chloride as a Lewis acid in acetic anhydride afforded the C-22 acetate **35** in 82% yield. To our surprise trimethylsilyl chloride and *t*-butyldimethylsilyl chloride also yielded the same C-22 acetate **35**, under similar reaction conditions. The ene reaction carried out using these Lewis acid catalysts stereospecifically generated the natural configuration at C-20. This approach makes use of the known preference for attack on the α -face of the C-17 (20) double bond and the highly ordered transition state of the ene reaction to set the stereochemistry of the C-20 carbon in natural configuration. The C-22 acetate was converted to the C-20 aldehyde using simple reaction sequence.

Stereoselective synthesis of (22*R*,23*R*,24*S*)-3 β -hydroxy-5-ene-22,23-dihydroxy-24-methylcholestan 49. A brassinolide intermediate from 16-dehydropregnenolone acetate

The aldehyde **31** synthesised from 16-dehydropregnenolone acetate **39** was stereoselectively converted¹⁵ to the triol **49**, a known brassinolide **1** intermediate (Scheme 4). The condensation of the aldehyde **31** with 2-lithio-1,3-dithiane gave stereoselectively the (22*R*)-alcohol **43** with small amount of the (22*S*)-alcohol. The C-22 alcohol group was acetylated and the dithiane moiety of **44** was deprotected with NBS/ $BaCO_3$ to get the acetoxy aldehyde **45**. The Wittig reaction on **45** with triphenylphosphoniumisobutyl bromide and *n*-BuLi in THF yielded the olefin **46** which on epoxidation followed by deprotection of *i*-methyl ether gave compound **48**. The epoxide ring of **48** was opened using trimethyl aluminium in the presence of *n*-BuLi in hexane and cyclohexane to give the triol **49**. Further elaboration of **49** to brassinolide **1** is well established^{7,17}. Thus this work constitutes a formal total synthesis of brassinolide **1**.

Short-step stereoselective synthesis of 2 α ,3 α ,22-triacetoxy-23,24-dinor-5 α -cholan-6-one 53. Key intermediate for the preparation of 24-norbrassinolide **3, dolicholide **4**, dolichosterone **9** and other brassinolide analogues**

Abe *et al.*¹⁸ isolated 24-norbrassinolide **3** from Chinese cabbage and Yokota *et al.*^{19,20} isolated dolicholide **4** and dolichosterone **9** from immature seeds of *Dolichos lablab* (Chart 2). Syntheses of 24-norbrassinolide **3**²¹, dolicholide **4**^{9,22,23}, and dolichosterone **9**^{9,22,23} are reported in the literature. The synthetic approaches developed for **3**, **4** and **9** are lengthy, consisting of protection and deprotection steps and often require exotic reagents.

The key intermediate 2 α ,3 α ,22-triacetoxy-23,24-dinor-5 α -cholan-6-one **53** has been synthesised by Mori *et al.*^{9,22}

Scheme 4. *Reagents and condition*: (a) 1,3-Dithiane, n-BuLi, THF, 0–20°, 3 h, (b) Ac₂O, pyridine, 30°, 24 h, (c) NBS, BaCO₃, aq. acetone, 25°, 1 h, (d) Ph₃PCH₂CH(Me)₂Br, THF, n-BuLi, 25°, 18 h, (e) *m*-CPBA, Na₂HPO₄, CH₂Cl₂, 25°, 6 h, (f) *p*-TSA, dioxane, H₂O, 60°, 2 h, (g) (CH₃)₃Al, n-BuLi, n-hexane, cyclohexane, –70–25°, 20 h.

in 11 steps in 6–10% overall yield, starting from stigmasterol and converting into brassinolide analogues. Takatsuto and Ikekawa²³ synthesised it in 13 steps in 29% overall yield and converted it into 24-norbrassinolide 3, dolicholide 4 and dolichosterone 9. In continuation of our efforts towards the synthesis of brassinosteroids, a simple and efficient synthesis²⁴ of the key intermediate 53 starting from 3 β -hydroxyandrost-5-en-17-one 32 has been carried out in

nine steps with an overall yield of 44% (Scheme 5).

Compound 35 synthesised from 32 is depicted in Scheme 2. The tosylate 35 was solvolysed with potassium acetate in aqueous acetone to give 3 α ,5-cyclo-6-hydroxy product 50 in excellent yield. The *i*-alcohol 50 was oxidised with Jones reagent and the corresponding 6-keto acetate was hydrogenated followed by mild acid catalysed rearrangement of the *i*-ketone to furnish the olefin 51 in three steps with an over-

Chart 2

Scheme 5. *Reagents and condition*: (a) Ph_3PEtI , KOBut , reflux, 6.5 h, (b) tosyl chloride, pyridine, 25° , 48 h, (c) resin, $(\text{CH}_2\text{O})_n$, Ac_2O , CH_2Cl_2 , 25° , 20 h, (d) KOAc , acetone-water, reflux, 3 h, (e) CrO_3 , acetone, 10° , 0.5 h, (f) Pd/C , H_2 , EtOH , 25° , 6 h, (g) PPTS , LiBr , DMF , reflux, 4 h, (h) OsO_4 , NMO , $t\text{-BuOH}$, acetone, 25° , 1.5 h, (i) Ac_2O , pyridine, $60\text{--}65^\circ$, 8 h.

all yield of 67%. Dihydroxylation of **51** with catalytic amount of OsO_4 and *N*-methylmorpholine-*N*-oxide (NMO), followed by acetylation afforded the triacetate **53** in two steps with

an overall yield of 97%. The transformation of this triacetate into 24-norbrassinolide **3**, dolicholide **4** and dolichosterone **9** have been documented^{9,22,23}. Our synthe-

Scheme 6. *Reagents and condition*: (a) $(\text{EtO}_2)\text{P}(\text{O})\text{CH}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{CHMe}_2$, NaH , C_6H_6 , reflux, 5 h, (b) MeLi , THF , -78° , 1 h, 20° , 4 h, (c) PCC , CH_2Cl_2 , 0° , 24 h, (d) TsOH , dioxane-water, 60° , 4 h.

sis²⁴ of triacetate **53** from dehydroepiandrosterone **32** thus constitutes a formal total synthesis of these brassinosteroids.

Synthesis of 3 β -hydroxy-24-methylcholesta-5,23-dien-22-one **61**. A brassinolide intermediate

The aldehyde **31** was readily available²⁵ from stigmasterol **54** in four steps with an overall yield of 92% via OsO₄ catalysed dihydroxylation of (22*E*)-olefin **55**, followed by Pb(OAc)₄ cleavage of the diol **56**. Horner-Wadsworth-Emmons reaction on the C-22 aldehyde **31**, furnished stereoselectively the (*E*)-enone **57** in 73% yield²⁶ (Scheme 6). The enone **57** on exposure to methyl lithium in THF gave a mixture (61% yield) of C-24 epimeric alcohols **58** and **59** in the ratio 4 : 1. Pyridinium chlorochromate oxidation²⁷ of tertiary allylic alcohols **58** and **59** separately or as a mixture, furnished the 1,3-carbonyl-transposed α,β -unsaturated ketone **60** in excellent yield (95%). Acid catalysed opening of **60** afforded 3 β -hydroxy-24-methylcholesta-5,23-dien-22-one **61** in 98% yield. Compound **61** has been prepared earlier by Takahashi *et al.*¹⁷ and the reported m.p., $[\alpha]_D$ and ¹H nmr data are in perfect agreement with those for the samples synthesised²⁶ by us. Transformation of this compound **61** to brassinolide **1** has been documented^{7,17}. Our synthesis of **61** thus constitutes formal synthesis of brassinolide **1**.

Stereoselective synthesis of (2*R*,3*S*,22*R*,23*E*)-6,6-ethylenedioxy-22-hydroxy-2,3-isopropylidenedioxy-24-methyl-5 α -cholest-23-ene **66**. An intermediate for the synthesis of castasterone and dolichosterone

From the insect gall (40 kg) of the chestnut tree, Yokota *et al.*²⁸ isolated castasterone **6** (95 μ g) and from the immature seeds (34 kg) of *Dolichos*, Baba *et al.*²⁰ isolated dolichosterone **9** (50 μ g) (Chart 3). Several syntheses of castasterone **6**, regarded as a biosynthetic precursor of

brassinolide are known. Mori *et al.*⁹ reported the first synthesis of dolichosterone **9** from readily available intermediate (2*R*,3*S*,22*R*,23*E*)-6,6-ethylenedioxy-22-hydroxy-2,3-isopropylidenedioxy-24-methyl-5 α -cholest-23-ene **66**. Recently, Back and Krishna²⁹ described the synthesis of the same intermediate **66** and elaborated it further to castasterone **6**. We have completed a simple, short and stereoselective, alternative synthesis of the intermediate **66** starting from stigmasterol (Scheme 7). The salient features of this synthesis are, a highly efficient Wittig olefination reaction on C-22 aldehyde **62**, to construct stereoselectively (*E*)-enone **63**, which was further elaborated to (2*R*,3*S*,22*R*,23*E*)-6,6-ethylenedioxy-22-hydroxy-2,3-isopropylidenedioxy-24-methyl-5 α -cholest-23-ene **66**, a known intermediate for castasterone **6** and dolichosterone **9**.

Chart 3

The known¹² aldehyde **62** was synthesised from stigmasterol in nine steps with an increased²⁵ overall yield of 41%. Wittig olefination of the aldehyde **62** with (3-methyl-2-oxobutyl)triphenylarsonium bromide, K₂CO₃ in CH₂Cl₂-THF-water at 25° for 22 h followed by flash chromatography on silica gel, afforded stereoselectively the desired (*E*)-enone **63** in 71% yield. Compound **63** on treatment with methyl lithium in THF at -78° for 1 h and at 20° for 4 h, furnished the alcohol **64** (61%) as oil. Pyridinium chlorochromate oxidation of the t-allyl alcohol **64** in CH₂Cl₂ at 0° for 23 h

Scheme 7. Reagents and condition : (a) (3-methyl-2-oxobutyl)Ph₃AsBr, K₂CO₃, CH₂Cl₂-THF-H₂O (25 : 10 : 0.5), 25°, 22 h, (b) MeLi, THF, -78°, 1 h, 20°, 4 h, (c) PCC, CH₂Cl₂, 0°, 24 h, (d) DIBAL-H, THF, -78°, 0.5 h.

Scheme 8. Reagents and condition: (a) *p*-TsCl, Py, 30°, 36 h, (b) CH₃COOK, acetone, water, reflux, 2 h, (c) Jones' reagent : 8 *N* CrO₃, acetone, 5°, 10 min, (d) *p*-TsOH-Py, DMF, reflux, 5 h, (e) TDTAP in CH₂Cl₂, *t*-BuOH, C₆H₅CH₂NMe₃OH in CH₂Cl₂, *t*-BuOH, 3°, 15 min, 28°, 1.5 h, (f) Ac₂O, Py, DMAP, 30°, 22 h, (g) F₃CC(O)OOH, CH₂Cl₂, Na₂HPO₄, 5°, 15 min, 25°, 12 h, (h) LiBr, Amberlyst-15, CH₃CN, 30°, 4 h, (i) Ac₂O, Py, DMAP, 30°, 40 h, (j) AcOH/H₂O (4 : 1), 90–100°, 16 h, (k) Ac₂O, Py, DMAP, 30°, 42 h, (l) K₂CO₃, MeOH, reflux, 4 h, followed by 2 *N* HCl, reflux, 1 h.

furnished the carbonyl transposed α,β -unsaturated ketone 65 which was stereoselectively reduced to the alcohol 66 using DIBAL-H in THF at -78° for 30 min.

New synthesis of 28-homobrassinolide 2 from stigmasterol

Among the various naturally occurring brassinosteroids, brassinolide 1 is the most active. 28-Homobrassinolide 2, differing from 1 only in the 24-alkyl group, is almost as active³⁰ as brassinolide 1. The unnatural (22*S*,23*S*)-28-homobrassinolide 67, readily obtained¹² from stigmasterol 54, is moderately active.

Starting from stigmasterol 54, synthesis of 28-homobrassinolide 2 has been reported by two groups in Japan. Takatsuto and Ikekawa³¹ completed the synthesis in 17 steps with an overall yield of 6.1%, while Sakakibara and Mori³² accomplished the synthesis in 13 steps with an overall yield of 12.1%. Both the groups used toxic and expensive OsO₄ for *cis*-dihydroxylation of 2,3-olefinic substrate. We have reported³³ a shorter and viable route for the synthesis of 28-homobrassinolide 2 from stigmasterol 54 in 12 steps with an overall yield of 15.6%, which uses tetradecyltrimethylammonium permanganate (TDTAP) for *cis*-dihydroxylation of 2,3-olefinic bond of compound 68 (Scheme 8).

The known (22*E*)-stigmasta-2,22-diene-6-one 68 was synthesised from stigmasterol 54 in four steps with an increased overall yield of 63%. *cis*-Dihydroxylation of 2,3-double bond of 68 by the known procedure¹² using catalytic amount of OsO₄ and *N*-methylmorpholine-*N*-oxide under controlled conditions invariably afforded a small amount of 2,3,22,23-tetraol. This observation was also made by McMorris *et al.*³⁴. The slightly less polar 2,3-diol 69

had to be separated from the more polar tetraol by column chromatography.

As a major achievement for the synthesis of homobrasinolides, we carried out a totally chemoselective *cis*-dihydroxylation of the diene **68** with TDTAP in $\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2/t\text{-BuOH}$ in the presence of benzyltrimethylammonium hydroxide as a base to obtain the $2\alpha,3\alpha$ -diol **69** along with some unreacted diene **68** which could be recycled. The yield of the diol **69**, on the basis of recovered starting material, was 32%. No trace of the tetraol was detected. Acetylation of the $2,3$ -diol **69** with acetic anhydride in pyridine in the presence of catalytic amount of 4-(dimethylamino)pyridine furnished the diacetate **70** in 99% yield. Baeyer-Villiger oxidation of **70** and epoxidation of its ($22E$)-double bond were effected in single step with trifluoroperoxyacetic acid in dichloromethane to give $22,23$ -distereomeric mixture of epoxy lactone **71** in 63% yield. Trifluoroperoxyacetic acid reacted very fast, even at ice-bath temperature and the ($22E$)-

olefin was consumed in less than 15 min.

Regioselective conversion³⁵ of the $22,23$ -epoxide **71** was carried out with LiBr and cation exchange resin Amberlyst-15 to furnish a mixture of *trans*-bromohydrins **72** and **73** in 91% yield in the ratio 61 : 39. They were separated by column chromatography on silica gel. The major isomer **72** is less polar than the minor isomer **73**. The catalyst could be filtered, activated and reused. Acetylation of the bromohydrin **72** afforded bromoacetate **74** in 92% yield. Nucleophilic substitution of 22 -bromo group of **74** producing 22 -hydroxy compound **76** was achieved in 83% yield using aqueous acetic acid, which was acetylated to furnish a mixture of the ($22R,23R$)-tetraacetate **78** and ($22S,23S$)-tetraacetate **79** in 85% yield. This mixture was separated by column chromatography to afford less polar minor isomer **79** and the more polar major isomer **78** in the ratio 38 : 62. Saponification of **78** with K_2CO_3 in aqueous methanol followed by acidification with 6 *N* HCl afforded the 28 -homobrasinolide **2** in 83% yield.

Scheme 9. Reagents and condition: (a) Pd/C, H_2 , 45 psi, 30° , 15 h, (b) KOH, *t*-BuOH, H_2O , 30° , 16 h, (c) TBDMSCl, imidazole, DMF, 30° , 8 h, (d) 1,3-dithiane, *n*-BuLi, THF, -40 – 0° , 24 h, (e) TBAF, THF, 30° , 2 h, (f) Hg_2Cl_2 , HgO, CH_3CN , H_2O , reflux, 6 h, (g) TsCl, Py, 30° , 12 h, (h) CH_3COOK , MeOH, reflux, 4 h, (i) LAH, THF, 0 – 25° , 2 h, (j) NaH, DMF, 60° , 2 h, EtI, 30° , 20 h, (k) PTSA, dioxane, H_2O , 50 – 60° , 4 h, (l) TsCl, Py, 30° , 12 h, (m) CH_3COOK , acetone, H_2O , reflux, 20 h, (n) 8 *N* Jones reagent, 0 – 5° , 15 min, (o) LiBr, PPTS, DMF, 150 – 160° , 4 h, (p) OsO_4 , NMO, *t*-BuOH, H_2O , acetone, 30° , 4 h.

The bromohydrin **73** was similarly converted to bromoacetate **75** in 93% yield. Compound **75** was transformed into mixture of tetraacetates through the triacetate **77** from which pure **78** and **79** were isolated in 83% yield in the ratio 73 : 27. This is an efficient synthesis³³ of highly potent 28-homobrassinolide **2** which paves the path for its large scale preparation, so that it may be used to increase the yields of a variety of agricultural crops.

Stereoselective synthesis of a new hexanor (C_{23} - C_{28})-castasterone-20,22-ethyl diether **93** from 16-dehydropregnenolone acetate and its plant growth promoting activity

Stereoselective synthesis of a new hexanor (C_{23} - C_{28}) castasterone-20,22-ethyl diether **93** has been achieved⁴⁰ in sixteen steps from cheap and readily available 16-dehydropregnenolone acetate. This new brassinosteroid has shown typical brassin activity in mung bean epicotyl bioassay.

Different qualitative structure-activity relationship proposed³⁶ earlier indicated that the structural requirements for a brassinosteroid to be biologically active are : a A/B *trans*-ring system (5α -H), a ketone or 7-oxa-6-keto system in ring-B, *cis*- α -oriented hydroxyl groups at C-2 and C-3, *cis*-hydroxyl groups at C-22 and C-23 as well as methyl or ethyl substituent at C-24. But this general proposition does not hold true in case of two reports^{37,38} where the synthetic brassinosteroids, lacking the required side-chain in one case and having unusual aryl substituent at C-23 in the other case, showed very high brassin activity. Kerb *et al.*³⁷ synthesised hexanor brassinolide-22-ethers which do not possess three asymmetric centers (C-22, C-23, C-24) of the brassinolide side-chain and yet show the plant growth promoting activity comparable to 28-homobrassinolide. Very

recently, Hayashi *et al.*³⁸ synthesised C-23 phenylbrassinosteroids with plant growth promoting activity surpassing that of parent brassinolide **1**. Brosa *et al.*³⁹ in 1996 synthesised four new brassinosteroids with $2\beta,3\beta$ -diol and A/B *cis*-ring junction elicited high activity as plant growth promoters. These authors proposed a new way to define the structural requirements for active brassinosteroids, from detailed molecular modelling study. According to them, the activity of brassinosteroids depends on the oxygen atoms spatial situation. Therefore, the structural requirements should not be indicated as the presence or not of the specific functional group in the molecule but as the spatial distribution of all the functionalities present in it. From all these reports and high activity of hexanorbrassinolide ethyl ether, it is evident that the alkyl chain (C_{23} - C_{28}) with three contiguous chiral centers at C-22, C-23 and C-24 might not be the necessary condition for a compound to show brassin activity. These literature precedences coupled with our continuous research efforts directed towards the synthesis of brassinosteroids from abundant steroidal precursors, prompted us to design new brassinosteroids, hexanor(C_{23} - C_{28})brassinolide-20,22-ethyl diether **96** and hexanor(C_{23} - C_{28})castasterone-20,22-ethyl diether **93** (Scheme 9). These new brassinosteroids⁴⁰ **93** and **96** are devoid of the usual six carbon (C_{23} - C_{28}) brassinolide side-chain and contain a *vic*-diether functionality at C-20 and C-22. This hexanorbrassinosteroid showed a considerable brassin activity in mung bean epicotyl bioassay.

16-Dehydropregnenolone acetate **39** has been chosen as starting material for this projected synthesis as it is widely available in India. The plant dioscorea cultivated in many parts of India, is an abundant source of diosgenin from which 16-dehydropregnenolone acetate is prepared commercially by Marker's procedure⁴¹. 16-Dehydropregnenolone acetate

Scheme 10

Scheme 11

39 was converted to its 3 β -*t*-butyldimethylsilyl ether 80 in three steps with 68% overall yield (Scheme 9). Compound 80 on treatment with 2-lithio-1,3-dithiane in THF at 0° gave stereospecifically the (20*R*)-hydroxydithiane 81 in 81% yield. Addition of 2-lithio-1,3-dithiane to 20-ketopregna derivatives is known⁴² to generate stereoselectively (20*R*) configuration at this center. Deprotection of the TBDMS group of compound 81 with tetrabutylammonium fluoride followed by removal of the dithiane moiety with HgCl₂/HgO/CH₃CN/H₂O furnished the dihydroxyaldehyde 83 (71%). Tosylation of the 3 β -hydroxy group of compound 83 and subsequent methanolysis of the tosylate 84 with dry methanol and fused KOAc afforded *i*-methyl ether 85 in 74% yield. Reduction of the C-22 aldehyde of compound 85 with LAH in THF at 0° afforded the C-20, C-22 diol 86. The diol 86 was converted to the ethyl diether 87 with ethyl iodide in DMF using NaH as a base (72%). Opening of the cyclopropane ring of 87 with catalytic amount of PTSA in aqueous dioxane gave the 3 β -alcohol 88 in 84% yield. Tosylation of the alcohol 88 followed by solvolysis of the tosylate 89 with KOAc/acetone/water furnished the *i*-alcohol 90 which was oxidised with 8*N* Jones reagent to give the *i*-ketone 91. Compound 91 was synthesised in 14 steps starting from 16-dehydropregnenolone acetate 39 in a respectable overall yield of 14.2%. But, the acid-catalysed rearrangement of the *i*-ketone 91 with LiBr, pyridinium-*p*-toluenesulfonate in refluxing DMF for 6 h gave the 2-ene-6-one 92 in poor yield (17%). Mild acid-catalysed rearrangement of the *i*-ketone 91 under variety of conditions failed to improve the yield of 92. In order to get the 2-ene-6-one 20,22-ethyl diether in quantity from 91, the following strategy was adopted.

Treatment of the *i*-ketone 91 with H₂SO₄-AcOH is expected³¹ to give the 3 β -acetoxy-6-keto-20,22-ethyl diether 97 which on alkaline hydrolysis followed by tosylation should afford compound 99 (Scheme 10). 2,3-Elimination of 99 with Li₂CO₃ in DMF should give the 2-ene-6-one 92. But the reaction of the *i*-ketone 91 with H₂SO₄-AcOH at 50° for 1 h afforded the 3 β -acetoxy-6-keto-22-aldehydes 100a and 100b as an inseparable mixture of C-20 epimers (68%) in almost 1 : 1 ratio. The epimeric aldehyde 100 was characterized by ir, nmr and mas spectroscopy. The expected compound 97 was not obtained in this reaction.

The conversion of the *i*-ketone 91 to the C-22 aldehyde 100 presumably takes place via the carbocations 101, 102 which forms the vinyl ether 103 (Scheme 11). This vinyl ether 103 under acidic conditions furnished the epimeric aldehydes 100a and 100b.

Compound 92 obtained in poor yield was osmylated with catalytic amount of OsO₄ and *N*-methylmorpholine-*N*-oxide to furnish hexanor(C₂₃-C₂₈)castasterone-20,22-ethyl diether 93 in 94% yield (Scheme 9). This new brassinosteroid was synthesised⁴⁰ in 16 steps from 16-dehydropregnenolone acetate. The biological activity of the new brassinosteroid 93 was determined using sensitive mung bean epicotyl growth bioassay⁴³ and it showed considerable brassin activity in mung bean epicotyl bioassay.

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